

Clinical and Experimental Datasets on Automated and Conventional Subjective Refraction

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) provides an overview of the research data generated within the project “Automated Vision Assessment Through Clinical Benchmarking: Towards Patient-Focused Vision Care” and describes how these datasets are structured, documented, stored, and made available for reuse by potential data users.

The project will generate several interrelated datasets derived from clinical measurements, experimental studies, and stakeholder input. These include:

- quantitative clinical data from a large cross-sectional study (approximately 1500 participants) comparing automated and conventional subjective refraction outcomes;
- longitudinal data assessing the effects of sustained near work on refraction results;
- detailed measurements of visual function, including accommodative and binocular parameters, pupil size, and ocular surface characteristics.

All datasets containing personal or clinical information will be anonymized, ensuring compliance with ethical requirements and applicable data protection regulations.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Automated Vision Assessment
Through Clinical
Benchmarking: Towards
Patient-Focused Vision Care

Researchers

Aiga Svede (0000-0002-9093-4282), Jelena Slabcova (0000-0003-0786-1471), Kristine Kalnica-Dorosenko (0000-0001-5947-9480), Gatis Ikaunieks (0000-0001-9328-7810), Inta Balode (0009-0008-4266-6026), Aļona Sumarokova (0000-0002-4563-9524), Anda Bišofa (0009-0009-4394-2915), Mariya Misri (0009-0003-2153-0983)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Clinical and Experimental Datasets on Automated and Conventional Subjective Refraction](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: Automated Vision Assessment Through Clinical Benchmarking: Towards Patient-Focused Vision Care

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

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Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of data collection is to evaluate the accuracy, reliability, and clinical applicability of automated subjective refraction systems and to identify factors influencing their performance. The generated data will support the project's objectives to compare automated and conventional methods, assess the impact of individual human factors and sustained near work, and develop evidence-based methodology and clinical guidelines for patient-focused use of automated vision assessment technologies.

The data will originate from controlled clinical studies and stakeholder input. Primary data will be collected through cross-sectional and longitudinal vision assessments conducted by certified optometrists, including measurements of subjective refraction, binocular and accommodative function, and ocular parameters. Additional data will be obtained through questionnaires capturing patient-reported outcomes and feedback from eye care professionals.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Clinical data
- Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Not considered

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data generated in this project will be useful for multiple stakeholder groups. Researchers in vision science, optometry, and biomedical engineering may use the datasets for secondary analyses, validation studies, and further development of automated vision assessment methods. Eye care professionals will benefit from insights into the clinical performance, limitations, and appropriate use of automated subjective refraction systems. Technology developers and industry stakeholders may use the data to improve algorithms, device design, and system transparency. Policymakers and healthcare regulators may use the results to support evidence-based decision-making and development of guidelines for the integration of artificial intelligence in vision care.

The datasets will be particularly valuable for understanding the role of human factors (e.g., accommodation and binocular vision) in automated refraction outcomes and for benchmarking automated systems against conventional clinical methods. Where possible, anonymized datasets and accompanying documentation will be made available to support reproducibility and reuse.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

CSV - Microsoft Excel, Google Sheets, LibreOffice Calc JSON

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Most of the data formats used in the project are open or can be made accessible for reuse in software applications and for recombination with other datasets.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

The data collected within the project "Automated Vision Assessment Through Clinical Benchmarking: Towards Patient-Focused Vision Care (No. Izp-2025/1-0169)" will be published within the Zenodo platform which is a free-of-charge, cross-disciplinary repository that is primarily used for scientific datasets but also for science-related software. The data will have restricted access and will be accessible for reuse upon request.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Gatis Ikaunieks (0000-0001-9328-7810)
- Aiga Svede (0000-0002-9093-4282)
- Kristine Kalnica-Dorosenko (0000-0001-5947-9480)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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